

Viscoelastic Analysis of Process-induced Stresses in Manufacturing of Thermoplastic Composites by Automated Fiber Placement Technology

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Abstract

Aerospace industry demands for better, faster, and more precise methods of manufacturing for structures. One of the most recently developed methods of manufacturing of composite structures is Automated Fiber Placement (AFP) that merges robotic technology with composite materials manufacturing. AFP allows for faster, more precise manufacturing, as well as more complex structures in terms of shape and geometry. To manufacture thermoplastic composites with AFP, it is necessary to increase the temperature of feeding tapes close to the melting point. This is to make the composite material tacky and moldable. Then the AFP roller deposits the tape in the location by applying pressure on it. After that the material deposition for the part is finished, the part has to cool down to the service temperature. Because of high temperature changes from melting to the room temperature, differences between material properties of composite and mold in modulus and coefficient of thermal expansion, non-isothermal cooling, and anisotropy of composite materials, there are process-induced stresses imposed on the composite structure. These stresses can result in major deformations and degradation in performance of composite structures.

One of the mechanisms behind the evolution of residual stresses is the differences between coefficient of thermal expansion of composite and that of mold. Upon cooling down of the composites to the room temperature the material changes properties and phases. There is a range of temperature that mechanical properties of thermoplastic resin is time-dependent, that is the modulus of resin changes (relaxes) under an applied strain. This viscoelastic behavior needs to be considered in the analysis of residual stresses.

In this work, we looked into process-induced stresses caused by interaction of mold and composites considering temperature dependency and time dependency behavior of composite materials and proposed a new numerical step-by-step scheme to take into account to mechanisms of stress generation and stress relaxation.

1 Introduction

With the combination of robotic technologies and composite materials, a new manufacturing technique emerged to the industry called Automated Fiber Placement (AFP). AFP machine consists of a robotic arm that locates the fiber placement head in the location and moves it around, it also applies pressure to the tapes that are laid on the part. AFP machine is capable of manufacturing both thermoset and thermoplastic composites. For thermoset manufacturing the machine only deposits the material on the mandrel and then the part is cured in autoclave for final production. However, for thermoplastic manufacturing the AFP machine also includes a heat source that increases the temperature of the tape just before it is deposited.

There are several advantages along with the drawbacks to this new technology that are yet to be studied. The main advantages of this technology are reproducibility and less labor intensity, and among

the drawbacks are complexity of the system that in turn can cause unwanted deformations on the part. For manufacturing large and complex structures this method is very promising and is being used in major aircraft manufacturing companies. Because the system is automatized the parts can be manufactured with higher precision and shorter time. Also, there are complex parts that are not producible with other manufacturing techniques, these parts include complex geometry parts and fiber-steered composite parts.

The main difference between thermoset and thermoplastic AFP manufacturing is that for the case of thermoplastic the consolidation process is done on the part while laying down the tapes; however, the thermoset AFP process requires two stages of laying down the tape and curing the thermoset resin. The focus of this study is thermoplastic composites manufactured by AFP. Automated Fiber Placement (AFP) technique has shown a great potential in manufacturing of thermoplastic composites due to the flexibility of the process in manufacturing large and complex structures. Furthermore, since the heating and pressure can be applied simultaneously and on the go, in-situ consolidation of the part can be achieved to avoid autoclave process. The schematic of thermoplastic fiber placement head of AFP shown in Fig. 1. There is a heat source that could be hot gas torch or other means of heating and the roller applies pressure on the thermoplastic tape and deposits it on the former layers. Because this AFP manufacturing involves heating, melting, and cooling steps development of residual stresses and strains is inevitable. These stresses are due to nonuniform and nonisothermal cooling, anisotropy, composite and mold interaction, high pressure gradient, and high processing temperature. There are several mechanisms involved in development of these stresses and it is important to keep these stresses and deformations within the allowable limit [1]. It is important to analyze and simulate these types of deformation in order to manufacture parts with better quality.

Residual stresses are inherent to most composite materials and influence the properties of composite structures. It is important to take into account the thermal residual stress in design and modeling of composite structures [2]. Residual stresses remain in the laminate and composite structures after processing and cooling process. They can be categorized in three different levels of *micro-mechanical*, *macro-mechanical*, and *global* level [3]. The residual stress in micro-mechanical or constituent level is mainly because of the mismatch between coefficient of thermal expansions of the fibers and the matrix. Thermoplastic composites, unlike thermosets, are heated to a processing temperature which is above its glass or melting temperature and consequently cooled and is solidified to the service temperature. The parts are often cooled to ambient temperature as service temperature. Unlike thermoset matrix composites, no chemical reaction occurs during the processing of thermoplastic matrix composites. However, individual plies in the stack must still be consolidated to form a laminate, that requires both high temperature and high pressure. The layup can be heated with different means such as quartz lamp, infrared lamp, or hot nitrogen gas torch. The consolidation time may vary from few seconds to few minutes, depending on the type of process and final application. The cooling results in volumetric shrinkage of thermoplastic matrix, that is much higher than the fiber shrinkage. In addition, the fiber shrinkage is anisotropic.

There are different mechanisms behind the residual stresses in the thermoplastic composites and composites in general, however the effects of these mechanisms often are linked and difficult to distinguish from each other. The material and structural parameters of residual stress depends on different parameters such as temperature difference (difference between cooling temperature and service temperature), coefficients of thermal expansion (and shrinkage), elastic coefficients of fiber, matrix, and the mold, fiber volume fraction, viscoelastic properties of the matrix, and temperature dependent properties of matrix. Among these properties, several are dominated by matrix properties either because of the nature of composite materials or because the fibers independent of the changing parameters. For example, stiffness in the transverse direction (E_2) is dominated by matrix properties because fibers in the transverse direction is not as stiff as in the longitudinal direction. And viscoelastic properties of composites are also dominated by the matrix because carbon fibers are not time-dependent and do not show viscoelastic properties.

Shrinkage in composites, mostly in the transverse direction, is dominated by the matrix shrinkage. The shrinkage in thermoplastic polymers depends on the morphology of the matrix (amorphous or semi-crystalline). In semi-crystalline thermoplastics, the volumetric shrinkage is because of the crystalline densification. Because the crystalline structure is denser and more packed than amorphous phase, the polymer become denser upon partial crystallization and solidification.

During cooling amorphous thermoplastic composites between the processing temperature and service temperature, the amorphous matrix is in the viscoelastic state. Viscoelastic state means that stresses can be relaxed with time. This happens because the molecular chains have enough energy and freedom of movement at high temperature. The relaxation in lower cooling rate (slower cooling downs) happens

to a more extent and better, because viscoelasticity is a time-dependent property and lower cooling rate gives the material more time to relax the stresses that are generated during cooling. For different thermoplastics, this viscoelasticity happens in different ranges of temperature. However; for most polymers this range is around the glass transition temperature (T_g). This means that above a certain temperature the material is very soft and inelastic and not incapable of bearing any loads and below that temperature the material starts to show elastic properties and be able to carry loads. This temperature that material transitions to the viscoelastic state called stress-free temperature (SFT). The SFT is often determined by heating the composite until the residual stresses were found to be zero. While cooling, the material below this temperature starts to generate residual stress. For PEEK, the SFT is dependent on the crystalline phase and peak crystallization temperature that itself is dependent on the cooling rate. It can be concluded that the temperature dependent properties of PEEK are also function of the rate of change of temperature and therefore dependent on time as well [4, 5].

As the material is cooling down, it passes through a temperature that the material becomes completely elastic and solidified completely. This means that the material no longer shows time dependent properties. This temperature can be critical for residual stress because the remainder of the stress (the stress that has not been relaxed) can not relax itself and “resides” or “freezes” in the material as the residual stress. The difference between stress free temperature and service temperature (elastic temperature) has a direct effect on the residual stress and the more this difference is the more residual stress we should expect. This residual stress can have major effects on the quality of manufactured parts.

There are different types of defects that are induced because of residual stress. Fiber waviness is one of the defects that can be associated with the residual stress. Fiber waviness can be defined as the deviations of fibers from the unidirectional laminate. Mandrel-part interaction, uneven pressure applied by the roller from AFP head, mismatch between CTEs, and high gradient of temperature through the thickness can cause the fiber waviness [6]. Fiber waviness degrades the compressive strength and other aspects of material performance.

The change in shape of composite structures after manufacturing is an inadvertent fault that happens because of lack of consideration of residual stresses. The origin of the change in the shape is the anisotropy of composites in shrinkage behavior during cooling, that itself originates from difference in thermal expansion of fibers and matrix. In the bigger scale of structure, in-plane contraction is much smaller than out-of-plane contraction for most composites [7]. Therefore, the shrinkage over the inner plies is more restrained during cooling. When the part is constrained in the mold, residual stresses begin to build up during cooling. Upon the demolding stage, the composite part is instantly deformed because of the residual stress [8]. In an angled structure the two sides of the part or curve approach each other and will result in the “spring-in” effect.

In addition, tool-part interaction, thermal gradients during cooling, and ply stacking sequence influence the spring-in of the laminate. geometrical parameters such as angle, part thickness and tool radius also play a role in the residual stress and spring-in effect. Models were developed to predict the final deformation, warpage or spring-in angle of the composite structure [7–10]. There are different approaches that used classical laminate theory (CLT), thermoelasticity, and viscoelastic behavior. Many of these studies utilize finite element analysis for stress and strain calculations. The main reason for development of these models is to be able to produce parts with minimal residual strain (spring-in) and stress and avoid trial-and-error based mold design.

The focus of this study is modeling of residual stresses and deformation of thermoplastic composite materials made by AFP technology, and the stresses caused by mismatch of properties of mold and composites.

2 Modeling and Analysis

Polymers show time-dependent properties, that in the case of manufacturing PEEK-Carbon composites are influential. PEEK shows viscoelastic properties in temperature between 40°C and 160°C that composites are manufactured in these temperatures. The viscoelastic properties mean that the stress decreases with time upon a constant applied strain. This is particularly important in analysis of process-induced residual stresses. For this purpose, we incorporated the viscoelastic properties of PEEK into analysis. Also, these properties are dependent on the temperature as well that will be discussed. The change in material properties (relaxation of modulus) can be described as the following,

$$E(t) = \sum_{i=1}^n E_i e^{-t/\tau_i} + E_\infty \quad (1)$$

Figure 1: Schematic of AFP manufacturing of thermoplastic composites.

in which the t is the time, τ is the relaxation time, and E_∞ is the relaxed modulus. From Boltzmann superposition one would get the following formula for change of stress with time for time-dependent materials.

$$\sigma(t) = \int_0^t E(t-\tau) \frac{d\varepsilon(\tau)}{d\tau} d\tau \quad (2)$$

Combining Eqs. 1 and 2 we will have

$$\sigma(t) = \int_0^t \left(\sum_{i=1}^n E_i e^{(\tau-t)/\tau_i} + E_\infty \right) \frac{d\varepsilon(\tau)}{d\tau} d\tau \quad (3)$$

which provides a basis for finite element analysis and stress relaxation. We used the relaxation properties of PEEK from [11] and the described FEM formulation to find viscoelastic properties of PEEK/Carbon composites. For this purpose, series of unit cell homogenization with FEM described in [12] were used to define properties of composites at different temperatures and also times.

Figure 2 shows the viscoelastic properties of Carbon/PEEK at different temperatures resulted from homogenization analyses.

Along the described stress relaxation mechanism, there is another mechanism that causes the generation of stresses. The stress generation in this case could be because of many different reasons, such as the non-isothermal cooling (different regions of structure cools down at different rates), difference between Coefficient of Thermal Expansion (CTE) of fiber and matrix in micro-level or difference in CTE of composite and the mold in macro-level. We focused on the latter, the stress generated in macrolevel by differences in CTE of composite and mold. To analyze this stress generation, we used thermoelastic FEM analysis to calculate the state of stress at different temperatures while cooling down (Fig 3). However, these two mechanisms (stress relaxation and generation) work against each other and the behavior of material is a function of material history and temperature. To capture both stress generation and relaxation an incremental numerical scheme was proposed. The flowchart (Fig 4) shows the numerical scheme that takes in to account for both stress generation and stress relaxation. For a typical step, first the stresses and deformations are calculated in an elastic step, then using the material properties relaxation (shown in Fig. 2), the calculated stresses will be relaxed. Then, a new analysis with a new geometry based on the deformations from previous step and stresses from relaxation calculation as the pre-stress field stress will start again until the final, cooled-down temperature is reached. With this numerical scheme, the stress generations because of mismatch between properties of composites and mold, along with specific time-temperature properties (viscoelastic properties at different temperatures) are considered in the calculations.

Figure 2: Viscoelastic properties of Carbon/PEEK composites at different temperatures.

Figure 3: Finite element thermoelastic analysis of composite and mold with updated geometry and relaxed pre-stress.

Figure 4: Flowchart of numerical algorithm with combination of stress generation and stress relaxation.

Figure 5: Change of stresses through the thickness of composite tapes, (a) change of σ_y (b) change of σ_x , and (c) change of σ_{xy} with regard to thickness and along the width of the tape. Part (d) depicts the placing of lines on which the stresses are calculated.

3 Results and Conclusions

Using the viscoelastic behavior of composites and the temperature-dependent elastic modulus and CTE in the described algorithm in previous chapter, we analyzed the state of stress as the result of manufacturing and interaction of mold and composite during cool down. The maximum stress in composite happens at the interface surface that is attached to the mandrel. Stresses at different temperature of cooling were calculated and shown in Fig. 5. Figure 5 shows the final cooled down state of stress at different heights and widths of composite tape. It can be seen that the state of stress for all types of stresses are more extreme on the edges or areas close to edges. This is because of boundary effect that is the area closer to the boundary are subjected to more stresses, and causes the inhomogeneity of stresses along the width and height of the tape. This is of course is in the lamina level, *meso-scale* as discussed in Chapter 1, but a similar mechanism happens in the macro level as well. The combination of these non-uniformities in lamina level and laminate and structure level that are inherent of AFP process causes a non-uniform residual stress in the part that might project itself in the form of deformations (e.g. deformation after demolding) or residual stress inside the material that would contribute to decreasing the strength of material or failure stress of structures.

Figure 6 depicts the change of strains along the width of the tape after the cool down is completed. As it can be seen the strains along the width is not uniform neither and depending on the location the strain would be different. It also shows that for ε_y the values are more extreme and higher close the edges and for ε_x the variations are less than those of ε_y but the more extreme strain happens in the middle. With the use of thermoelastic analysis we also calculated this strain (ε_y) at different temperatures along of the cooling that is shown in Fig 7.

Figure 7 shows the evolution of strain on top of tape at different temperatures. It shows that with decrease in the temperature the magnitude of strains are becoming larger the average of strains on top of the tape at different temperatures is shown in Fig. 8.

Figure 9 shows different cooling rate and time. The absolute value of stress increases as the material cools down, however, the rate of this increase is different for different cooling and manufacturing scenarios. As it can be seen the longer the part stays in the viscoelastic temperature range, more of the generated stress can relax. The prolonged cooling time shows that with more time in cooling process the stress will increase even further. With this tool we can find the state of stress with different manufacturing procedures and find an accurate state of residual stress.

Figure 6: Change of strain through the width of composite tapes, (a) change of ε_y (b) change of ε_x , and (c) change of ε_{xy} along the width of the tape. Part (d) depicts the placing of lines on which the strains are calculated.

Figure 7: Strain on top of the tape at different temperatures along the width of the tape.

Figure 8: Average strain on top of the tape at different temperatures.

Figure 9: Change of average stress on top of the tape at different temperatures with different cooling times.

In this research, we studied and analyzed the stresses that are created because of the interaction of mold and composite. We considered the viscoelastic properties of composite as well as the temperature dependent properties. Because two main phenomena of stress generation and stress relaxation are happening concurrently, an algorithm was proposed to take into the account both of them. Using this algorithm accurate state of stress can be calculated and used in the design.

This method can be used for two main purposes. First, it can be used for understanding the manufacturing process and finding sources of residual stresses and magnitude of these stresses depending on the manufacturing scenario and their effects on the final part. Secondly, finding optimal cooling process and manufacturing scenario to minimize residual stresses or unwanted deformations. Designers can use this type of calculations to minimize the wanted deformations and stresses that leads to better structures.

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